

THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract: In recent years, modern technologies have played a key role in the educational process, especially in learning foreign languages. The use of digital tools and online resources in teaching English to university students is significantly changing approaches to teaching and learning. This article examines the methods of technology implementation in English language teaching, their advantages and challenges.

Keywords: modern technologies, teaching methods, digital tools, tutorials, gamification, student engagement.

To study the use of modern technologies in English language teaching, an analysis of literary sources was carried out, including research on teaching methods and practical experience of universities actively using digital tools. The opinions of teachers and students on the impact of technology on the learning process were also collected.

Modern technologies offer a wealth of advantages for English language teaching, transforming the learning experience for university students. Interactive platforms and software provide personalized learning experiences, catering to individual needs and learning styles. Online simulations and games engage students in a more immersive and stimulating manner, making the learning process more enjoyable. These tools also offer immediate feedback, allowing students to track their progress and identify areas for improvement. Moreover, technology facilitates access to diverse learning resources, including authentic materials, multimedia content, and interactive exercises, enriching the learning experience and fostering a deeper understanding of the language. By embracing technology, educators can create more engaging and effective learning environments, empowering students to become more confident and proficient communicators in English. The analysis showed several key methods and advantages of using technology in English language teaching:

- Video tutorials and webinars: Audio and video materials make learning more visual and accessible, allowing students to develop listening skills.
- Simulations and games: The gamification of learning through interactive games and role-playing simulations promotes the practical application of language in a variety of situations.
- Cloud technologies: Platforms such as Google Classroom provide access to educational materials and facilitate interaction between teachers and students.
- Mobile Apps: Using mobile language learning apps allows students to study anytime, anywhere, which increases learning flexibility.
- Modern technologies provide access to a variety of educational resources and methods, which allows you to individualize learning and adapt it to the needs of each student. However, in order to successfully integrate technology into the learning process, it is necessary that teachers are well trained and have access to the necessary resources.

Among the challenges are technical problems, lack of infrastructure and differences in the level of digital literacy of students.

The use of modern technologies in English language teaching provides significant benefits, including increasing student engagement and improving their language skills. It is important that educational institutions actively develop the skills of teachers and provide access to modern tools. Future research may focus on assessing the long-term effects of technology implementation in the learning process and how they affect student academic performance.

In conclusion, modern technologies play an important role in teaching English to university students, significantly improving the quality of education and preparing students for the requirements of the modern world.

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